

Research

Transportation of Root Canal Using Three Types of Rotary Instrument: An in Vitro Study

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Abstract: This study evaluates the transportation in severe curve root canals after preparation with three types of rotary file systems. Thirty-six human permanent mandibular 1st molars, freshly extracted for periodontal reasons, with curve mesial root, were selected and kept in normal saline. Mesial roots were separated from the tooth and removal of the crown was to standardize length at 12mm. Teeth were divided into three groups; mesio buccal canal of group A was instrumented with rotary variable taper instruments, group B was instrumented with reciprocating variable taper instruments, Group C was instrumented with rotary constant taper control memory instruments. All canals were shaped and cleaned under frequent and abundant irrigation with 5.25% sodium hypochlorite solution and 17% ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) followed by normal saline. Preoperative & postoperative Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) was taken to measure the transportation of the root canal. Transportation was calculated according to the formula of Gambill et al., (1996) $(x_1 - x_2) - (y_1 - y_2)$ where x_1 and x_2 represent the shortest pre-instrumentation and post-instrumentation mesial distances, respectively, and y_1 and y_2 represent the shortest pre instrumentation and post instrumentation distal distances, respectively. Statistical analysis among three groups was performed by the Kruskal-Wallis test and Wilcoxon test used for multiple pairwise comparisons among different groups. Value $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The transportation of root canal in the group C was found least than in the group B and group A. In conclusion, a rotary constant taper control memory instrument showed less transportation than a rotary variable taper instrument and reciprocating variable taper instrument.

Keywords: Curve canal, Rotary Instrument, CBCT, Transportation

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Introduction

Biomechanical preparation is one of the most important steps of root canal therapy. The aim is to form a continuously tapered shape with the smallest diameter at the apical foramen and the largest at the orifice to allow effective irrigation and filling and maintain the original canal curvature. (1). It influences the overall success of the treatment itself. (2).

The root canal morphology is not always as straight, various curves are present along the length of the canal (3). According to the degree of root canal curvature: straight is less than 5°; moderate: 10-20°; and severe: 25-70°. (4).

Biomechanical preparation of the curved root canals becomes very difficult for a clinician. The curvature of the canal is considered to be the preeminent risk factor for procedural errors like ledging, zipping, and transportation. (5). Canal transportation is defined in the American Association of Endodontists' Glossary of Endodontic Terms as "the removal of canal wall structure on the outside curve in the apical half of the canal due to the tendency of files to restore themselves to their original linear shape during canal preparation". Transportation occurs due to the tendency of endodontic instruments to straighten of root canal during the biomechanical preparation. (6,7).

Traditionally stainless-steel instruments were used for root canal shaping but they are stiff and fail to achieve the desired root canal shape, especially in narrow and curved canals. 46% of curved canals have varying degrees of apical transportations subsequent to instrumentation. (8).

Recently technologically advanced rotary nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) instruments such as continuous rotary variable taper, reciprocating variable taper, and continuous rotary constant taper instruments have new designs with different kinematics have been introduced. The manufacturer claims that above mention instruments maintain the original canal shape with considerably less procedural error.

The continuous rotary variable taper, (Protaper Gold) is a multi-file system comprised of 3 shaping files (SX, S1, and S2) and 5 finishing files (F1-5). Progressive taper, variable pitch, helical angle, and modified noncutting tips increase the flexibility of the instrument for curve canal preparation (9).

Reciprocating variable taper, (Wave One Gold) is a single file system in reciprocating motion developed from M-wire (10). Primary (tip size/taper: #25/0.07). Each file has an alternating offset parallelogram-shaped cross-section and a semi-active guiding tip. Another unique design feature is that each file has a fixed taper from D1-D3, yet a progressively decreasing percentage taper tapered design from D4-D16, which serves to preserve dentin & maintained the curvature without distorting the shape of the root canal (10).

Continuous rotary constant taper (Orodeka Plex V) is a multi-file system Orifice Opener (15/0.8), PLEX V 15/.03, Plex V 20.04, PlexV 25.04, characteristics of these files are controlled memory alloy, shape memory, non-active tip, and a convex triangular section modified with a wide and deep space between the blades, these instruments are widely used for curve root canal preparation. Control memory wire has lower nickel content (52%), thus softening the metal, which would likely make the instrument less aggressive in cutting and hence more likely to stay centered during instrumentation and less chance of deviation of canal curvature (11).

CBCT is non-invasive technique for the analysis of canal geometry after biomechanical preparation (12,13).

Therefore, the present study is designed to measure transportation after preparation with these three types of rotary instruments by using CBCT respectively.

Research Methodology

After obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of BSMMU, this Prospective Quasi-Experimental study was conducted in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, BSMMU from September 2021 to August 2022. The study population was the patient who attend the Maxillofacial department at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University need extraction of teeth for periodontal treatment. The study sample was mesiobuccal canal of the human mandibular permanent molar tooth with mesiobuccal canals having 25°-40° curvature. Radiographs of

teeth in both the buccolingual and mesiodistal directions were taken for selecting the right samples. The tooth with an open apex, root resorption, calcification, and curvature below 25° was excluded from the study.

Extracted lower Ist permanent molar teeth were collected and stored in normal saline until use. Marking the mesiobuccal side of the teeth and mesial root was separated from the distal root through bifurcation using diamond discs. The Crown was removed by diamond discs to a standardized mesial root 13mm.. Separated mesial roots were arranged in the occlusal rim to be scanned for CBCT. Patency was checked by 10 no K files. Working length determination was done by placing a 10-size K file (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) at the apical foramen which could be visualized of the tip at the apical foramen viewed under magnification loupes. Subtracting 1mm from the length.

The teeth were then divided into three groups. A- group (Continuous rotary variable taper file (Pro taper Gold), B- group reciprocating variable taper file (Wave one Gold), C- group continuous rotating 4% constant taper control memory file (Orodeka Plex V File).Glidepath was made by 10no-kfiles. Glidepath was expanded to rotary 2% 15 no file Proglider (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland);

Group A was instrumented with continuous rotary variable taper Ni-Ti files (Pro taper gold, Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland).

Group B was instrumented with a reciprocating variable taper Ni-Ti instrument (Wave One Gold), by reciprocating endo motor (Canal Pro, CL2, Coltene)

Group-C was instrumented with continuous rotary constant taper Ni-Ti files (4% Orodeka Plex V File). Finally, the canals were dried with sterilized paper points.

All canals were prepared by only the researcher. After instrumentation, arranging specimens in occlusal rimspecimens were included for taking CBCT.Three cross-section planes at levels 3, 5, and 8 mm from the apical end of the root were viewed through the explorer mode. The pre-instrumented and post-instrumented shortest distances from the canal's edge to the root's periphery were measured in mesial and distal directions by using One Clinic 3D by Osteem. Transportation was calculated according to the formula of Gambill et al. (1996): $(x_1 - x_2) - (y_1 - y_2)$, where x_1 and x_2 represent the shortest pre-instrumentation and post-instrumentation mesial distances, respectively, and y_1 and y_2 represent the shortest pre instrumentation and post instrumentation distal distances, respectively.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS version 26(IBM, Armonk, US). Statistical analysis among three groups was performed by the Kruskal-Wallis test and Wilcoxon test used for multiple pairwise comparisons among different groups. Value $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

All the parameters were not normally distributed (Table I).

Comparison of transportations (mm) among three groups performed by Kruskal Wallis's test which indicates statistically insignificant at apical 3mm, middle 5mm, and coronal 8mm (table II). Group B showed transportation at coronal 8mm which directed to furcation but no transportation at apical 3mm and middle 5mm. Group C showed transportation at apical 3mm which directed laterally to curvature and there was no transportation at middle 5mm and coronal 8mm. Group A showed an equal amount of transportation at apical 3mm, middle 5mm, and coronal 8mm directed laterally.

The comparison of transportation at apical 3mm, middle 5mm, and coronal 8mm in each individual group were not significant.The comparison of transportation at apical 3mm, middle 5mm, and coronal 8mm between group A and group B, group B and group C, and group A and group C, were not significant (Table III)

Table I: Tests of normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	p-value	Statistic	df	p-value
Transportation at 3 mm	0.318	36	0.000	0.721	36	0.000
Transportation at 5 mm	0.338	36	0.000	0.800	36	0.000
Transportation at 8 mm	0.196	36	0.001	0.856	36	0.000

All the parameters were not normally distributed ($p < 0.05$).

P-value is < 0.05 considered significant.

Table II: Comparisons of the transportation (mm) at the different levels among three groups

Level	Group A (n=12) Mean±SD	Group B (n=12) Mean±SD	Group C (n=12) Mean±SD	P value
Apical (3mm)	0.04±0.09 (0.02)	0.00±0.03 (0.0)	0.04±0.07 (0.01)	0.229
Middle (5mm)	-0.05±0.14 (-0.02)	0.01±0.02 (0.0)	-0.02±0.09 (0.0)	0.307
Coronal (8mm)	-0.03±0.05 (-0.02)	-0.07±0.11 (-0.01)	-0.01±0.17 (0.0)	0.502
p-value	0.066	0.020	0.413	

Table III: Comparison of transportations (mm) at a different level between groups (N=36)

Transportation	Wilcoxon test		
	Group A vs B p-value	Group A vs C p-value	Group B vs C p-value
3 mm	0.373	1.000	0.373
5 mm	0.385	1.000	1.000
8 mm	0.790	1.000	0.805

The p-value obtained by the Wilcoxon test

Figure-1: Pre and post instrument CBCT analysis in Group A at 3mm

Figure-2: Pre and post instrument CBCT analysis Group B at 3mm

Figure-3: Pre and post instrument CBCT analysis Group C at 3mm

Discussion

The mean of transportation at apical 3mm, middle 5mm & coronal 8mm was not statistically significant in group A (canal prepared by a continuous rotary variable taper), group B (canal prepared by a reciprocating variable taper), and group C (canals prepared by a continuous rotary constant taper control memory).

Transportation between 0.15mm to 0.3mm is acceptable (14). Positive values indicate the direction of transportation at the lateral side negative value indicate the direction at the furcal side. In the present study, apical 3mm of group A was (Mean \pm SD 0.04 \pm 0.09), group B was (Mean \pm SD 0.00 \pm 0.03) and group C was (Mean \pm SD, -0.04 \pm 0.10). In this study, no one group exceeded the acceptable range.

Comparison of mean transportation between group C & group A was not significant at apical 3mm, middle 5mm & coronal 8mm. But group A showed transportation lateral to curvature (mean \pm SD 0.04 \pm 0.09) at apical 3mm, (-0.05 \pm 0.14) at middle 5mm, (-0.05 \pm 0.14) at coronal 8mm middle (15). The previous study (15) also found insignificant transportations between constant taper rotary instrument (Twisted adaptive) (Mean \pm SD; 0.07 \pm 0.06) & variable taper rotary instrument (Mean \pm SD; 0.07 \pm 0.06). The finding was consistent with the present study.

The comparison of mean transportation between group C & group B was not statistically significant at apical 3mm, middle 5mm & coronal 8mm. (Table V). (16). In the previous study, revealed no significant difference in mean of transportation between constant taper rotary instruments (twisted files) & reciprocating variable taper instruments (wave one file). The result of the previous study was consistent with the present study. In the previous study, the reciprocating variable taper instrument showed a lower mean of transportation at the apical portion, and in the present study, group B showed a lower mean of transportation at apical 3mm, middle 5mm than coronal 8mm. It could be due to increased diameter and decreased flexibility of the instrument at the coronal portion. In the previous study, the rotary constant taper instrument (twisted files) showed a statistically significant difference in mean transportation among the three-level. In the present study, group C showed a lower mean of transportation at middle 5mm and coronal 8mm, and apical 3mm but not statistically significant among the three levels. It could be due to the

new manufacturing method, which resulted in increased phase transformation temperature and increased flexibility of the new file (7).

The comparison of mean transportation between group A & group B was not statistically significant at apical 3mm, middle 5mm & coronal 8mm (Table V). In the present study, group A showed transportation among three levels but was not statistically significant but group B showed lower transportation at apical 3mm and middle 5mm than at coronal 8mm. In the previous study (17) reciprocating variable taper demonstrated less canal transportation than the rotary variable taper group at the apical level. The finding of the previous research was consistent with the present study: The previous study (18) recorded that the mean transportation was not significant between the variable taper rotary instruments & variable taper reciprocating instruments. The result of the previous study was consistent with the present study.

Conclusion

Based on the present study, a rotary constant taper control memory instrument showed less transportation than a rotary variable taper instrument and reciprocating variable taper instrument.

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Ethical Issue

This research protocol was approved by the committee and permission for the study was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU/2021/8578).

Conflict of interest

~~Authors declare no conflict of interest.~~

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